

(PA 123: Local Government and Decentralization)

The state of local government and decentralization in Bangladesh: How is the process going?

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Introduction

The role of local government in every government is critical. It is crucial in putting central government plans into action at the local level. Typically, local government is established to respond to the needs of the local community by providing and delivering essential services. Local government is a public organization authorized to decide and administer a limited range of public policies within a relatively small territory which is sub-division of the regional or national government (Siddiqui, 2014). Local government (LG) is an integral part of the system of government because it refers to a political subdivision of a nation or state which is constituted by law and has substantial control of local affairs, including the power to impose taxes or exact labor for prescribed purposes. It has previously been observed that sometimes local government has been mistakenly considered as local governance which refers to the application of various governance criteria (accountability, transparency, efficiency, participation, equity, etc.) to all important and relevant development-oriented local organizations or efforts, such as local government bodies, local administration, local NGOs, cooperatives, local media, informal community activities, etc. (Siddiqui, 2014). On the other hand, Decentralization is the transfer of planning, decision making, and administrative authority from central government to field organizations, local administrative units, semi-autonomous and para-statal organizations, or NGOs (Cheema and Rondinelli, 1983).

Local administration in Bangladesh has a long history and tradition dating back to the Middle Ages. The British, on the other hand, were the ones who created the contemporary form of municipal government. Village groups were recognized as vital local government groups after the Bengal Local Self-Government Act was passed in 1885. The Local Government Act was passed in 1997, while the Upazila and Zilla Parishad Acts were passed in 1998 and 2000, respectively. These changes transferred power and resources from the federal government to the division, district, sub-district, and union levels, ushering in a new age of decentralization.

Local government is defined as the self-government of a community that is accountable to the people. It has its own budget, legal status, specific functions, and decision-making authority, and it manages local affairs. The first local government organization in Bangladesh was established by Britain. Bangladesh was subsequently absorbed into Pakistan following the partition. The structure of local government was altered under these two governments. Following the war with Pakistan, Bangladesh became independent in 1971. Many political regimes have risen to power and remained in power since the country's independence. The local

administration system has undergone several changes. So far, the reforms initiated by different political regimes are subject to a great deal of criticism.

This paper's main goal is to investigate the condition of decentralization within local government entities. This work is mostly based on a review of secondary materials. The history and reformation of local government in Bangladesh will be discussed in this article. In addition, this article will explore the local government's financial mechanism as well as the collaboration between the central and local governments.

Constitutional and Legal Basis of LG in Bangladesh

Bangladesh's constitution is the most significant dedication of independence to the nation's people. There is provision for local government organizations as one of the organs of the government to create democratic standards and to determine social and financial progress of the population (Khan, 2009). Three Local Government articles form a fundamental pillar of Bangladesh's constitution. The three articles are:

Article 11. “The Republic shall be a democracy in which fundamental human rights and freedoms and respect for the dignity and worth of the human person shall be guaranteed, and in which effective participation by the people through their elected representatives in administration at all levels shall be ensured.”

Article 59. “(1) Local Government in every administrative unit of the Republic shall be entrusted to bodies, composed of persons elected in accordance with law. (2) Everybody such as is referred to in clause (1) shall, subject to this constitution and any other law, perform within the appropriate administrative unit such functions as shall be prescribed by Act of Parliament, which may include functions relating to-

- (a) administration and the work of public officers;
- (b) the maintenance of public order;
- (c) the preparation and implementation of plans relating to public services and economic development.”

Article 60. “For the purpose of giving full effect to the provisions of article 59 Parliament shall, by law, confer powers on the local government bodies referred to in that article, including the power to impose taxes for local purposes, to prepare their budgets, and to maintain funds.” (The Constitution of the People’s Republic of Bangladesh, n.d.)

Since Bangladesh's independence, LGIs have only existed at one level: the Union Level. After an 18-year gap, the second-tier Upazila or subdistrict was established in 2009. Since independence, the Zila Parishad, or District Council, has not been renewed in its democratic form. At the divisional level, the LGI has never been a source of worry in Bangladesh. In the Pakistani era, there were LGIs at the divisional level, as part of the core democratic system. (Panday, 2011)

Finance for local government in Bangladesh

Fiscal decentralization refers to the financing of local government. The devolution of financial authority to regional and local governments is known as fiscal decentralization. Fiscal decentralization addresses two challenges that are intertwined. To begin with, it depicts the various levels of government's expenditure obligations and revenue sources (national, regional, local). Second, it depicts the choice made by the national and local governments to calculate their total and detailed expenditures and income. Both of these challenges have a significant impact on the political and administrative certainty of decentralization.

Smoke (2001), has identified four pillars of fiscal decentralization. These are:

- ❖ Expenditure responsibilities: Each level of government's expenditure obligations and functions must be specified.
- ❖ Revenue assignments (including tax sources): Local governments will be given tax or non-tax income streams to supply them with resources after they have been assigned specific expenditure duties.
- ❖ Intergovernmental fiscal transfers: Through a system of intergovernmental fiscal transfers or grants, central governments can offer additional resources to regional and local governments.
- ❖ Sub-national borrowing: Failure of the subnational government to match its yearly spending with income and transfers would result in subnational deficits and debt incursion through borrowing.

➤ What are the Benefits of Fiscal Decentralization?

Fiscal decentralization allows people to make their own decisions. People are given more freedom and discretion in making decisions. Local government already has a strong relationship with the people of the area. Fiscal decentralization strengthens ties between local governments and citizens. People's willingness to pay taxes improves as a result of fiscal decentralization, which boosts their participation in democratizing local government. It strengthened local government entities' responsibility to the public, resulting in increased openness and efficiency as well as increased working efforts. Local governments were less reliant on the central government for funding as a result of fiscal decentralization recovering the majority of their costs. People receive better services as a result of this, and this establishes excellent authority.

➤ Fiscal Decentralization in Bangladesh

The ability of a local government to receive adequate money from the local economy and then select how to spend that money is referred to as fiscal autonomy. Local government fiscal autonomy refers to a jurisdiction's ability to set tax rates and build a revenue base without outside intervention, as well as the power to provide the quality of service that its residents desire.

Revenue assignment, Borrowing and Fiscal transfer, Expenditure responsibility, Precondition of democracy, Human resource are the components of local government fiscal decentralization in Bangladesh:

❖ Revenue assignment

Local governments in Bangladesh struggle to generate revenue because they have limited control over tax and fee rates. Local governments are unable to pursue and implement as many development projects as they would want, as well as offer basic services to local populations, due to inadequate tax collection and inadequate funds from the national government. As a result, local administrations depend largely on central government payments. On this front, the restricted tax base and slowness in the revenue collecting procedure see as the key barriers.

Taxes, however, are the most important source of revenue for municipal governments in Bangladesh. At the moment, there are two methods for collecting local taxes and fees: local governments collecting them themselves and the central government collecting them on their behalf. The central government distributes a percentage of the money received in relevant jurisdictions with the local government in the latter situation. Local administrations in Bangladesh, on the other hand, are often efficient in collecting taxes. People cannot afford to pay taxes, according to local government justifications, yet this may be indicative of a lack of political will and excuses for poor management (Fox and Menon 2008).

❖ Borrowing and fiscal transfer

Bangladeshi local governments are not permitted to borrow. According to the World Bank, local government revenue is less than 1% of GDP in 2019, but because LGIs are unable to borrow, LGs rely on central government revenue. There is also an insufficient flow of funds from the central government to local governments. Only 7% of GDP is allocated to local governments in the fiscal year 2020-21 (ADP). Under Bangladesh's Yearly Development Programme, the central government is responsible for delivering a significant annual budgetary transfer to local governments in the form of block grants (ADP). ADP funds the development budget of the central government, which is financed by the surplus revenue budget, domestic borrowing, external borrowing, and aid from donor agencies. The transfers through the ADP are segmented into four major expenditure classifications: sector/program allocation, block allocation, self-financed allocation, and food assistance (Fox and Menon 2008).

❖ Expenditure responsibility

In Bangladesh, elected local governments have been given comparatively limited expenditure powers. Local governments in Bangladesh have limited authority for basic and secondary education, fire safety, and basic health care, among other policy areas. In a decentralized system, responsibilities for services are significantly greater at the municipal, Upazila Parishad, and city corporation levels. However, rather than local government officials, ministry workers who operate in these offices offer services on behalf of their respective ministries. Local governments' ability to offer services is severely hampered by a lack of resources and institutional capacity (Fox and Menon 2008).

❖ Precondition of democracy

In Bangladesh, there is a heavy centralization in terms of the relative size and independence of local governments. Local governments enjoy very limited decision-making autonomy, which is evidenced on both the expenditure and revenue sides of their budgets. Local Government Division must approve annual local government budgets (Fox and Menon 2008). Projects must usually be approved by higher-level governments before they can be implemented. The central government sets the tax and fee rates. Local government discretion is limited, which restricts operational jurisdictions and local government institutions' overall autonomy, as well as creating role ambiguity across different levels of government. Furthermore, the power of local government decision-making is susceptible to central control. Local governments lack functional autonomy since the central government control expenditure choices and grant allocations to local government organizations.

As a result, the relationship between government bodies and the general people is shaky. Furthermore, fiscal decentralization in local government is of poor quality. Because of the central government's supremacy, there is no local democracy. Local government and government employees are at odds.

❖ Human resources

The shortage of trained human resources in Bangladesh is a problem impacting local government performance. Local governments have no human resource autonomy. The central government or its subordinate entities that operate at the division or district level appoint officials. In essence, all local government personnel are Ministry of Public Administration personnel who report to and are accountable to their respective central government entities rather than the local government where they are employed. Appointing new workers requires clearance from the Local Government Division, which is typically difficult to get. Notably, the federal government determines the staff arrangements for municipalities and city corporations. A chief executive officer is seconded from the central civil service to each municipal corporation (UNESCAP 1999). All other officials, whether hired directly by the municipal corporation or temporarily, will report to the chief executive officer. Except for united parishes, local government entities have deputies that represent various ministries within the federal government. Their parent ministry establishes the conditional relationships that bind their services. Officials and workers appointed by union parishads and Upazila Parishads, on the

other hand, adhere to the service norms established by these organizations. Similarly, officials nominated by municipalities and city corporations on a local level adhere to their particular local service standards. The Ministry of Local Government, Rural Development, and Cooperatives serve as the primary personnel agency for municipal and city corporation functions.

In Bangladesh, there are also several issues with fiscal decentralization in the local government system. The local government has little authority over tax revenue. The local government is ineffective when it comes to collecting taxes from its constituents. Political outrage and a problematic land record. Locals are adamant about not paying their fair share of taxes. Local government entities are not turning up to collect taxes because citizens are unwilling to pay them. As a result, there would be a tragedy of the commons between local residents and the government. The local government of Bangladesh is not allowed to borrow. As a result, the local administration is completely reliant on the central government for funding. Expenditure autonomy of local government is limited and civil servants provide the services. There is also a clash between civil servants and local government. Because, civil servants are not accountable to local government, they are accountable to the central government. Human resources and capacity of local government are limited. Central government provides human resources for local government. So, they are accountable to the central government. Finally, the pre-condition of fiscal decentralization is democracy which is at the poor level in Bangladesh. Because of the dominance of central government.

Central-Local Relation in Bangladesh

Local governments in Bangladesh are limited to the powers granted by the central government. In Bangladesh, there is a patron-client relationship between the central and local governments. There is a dominant type relationship between central and local government. Central government dominates local government in various ways. Central government control local government through power. Local government is powerless without central government. Local government is accountable to the central government for its work. Local government needs approval from the central government.

The central government fixes the structure, composition, and tenure of local government bodies through various legislation; the mode of administering the oath and removing functionaries; the sources of funds and their expenditure pattern; the method of levying taxes, rates, and fees,

among other things; the preparation of budgets; the functions, powers, duties, and roles of various local government functionaries; and the personnel system and personnel management. The central government also creates specific regulations for election administration, business, Chairmen's rights and responsibilities, tax assessment, budget preparation, personnel hiring, accounting and auditing, and many other key sectors. Local government entities, on the other hand, have the authority to enact rules. However, they must be approved by the central government (Siddiqui,2005)

Bangladesh's central-local connections have long been a source of debate. Central-local bonds have always been authoritative, according to the law. This might be due to the colonial legacy and the lack of democratic governance at the national level for a long time. The central government controls local governments largely through field-level bureaucrats such as local chief executive officers or secretaries, as well as the heads of other district administration agencies participating in local government operations. The central government also exercises significant financial and administrative control over local governments in different ways. This is especially the case in the allocation of resources. For the financing of development projects, local governments depend fully on central government grants. In the allocation of grants, the central government has often acted beyond its power. The allocation of grants depends on the existing relationship between a local government and the central government (Panday,2006).

Forms of Decentralization

In terms of nature coverage and authority, the manner of decentralization varies from nation to nation. Political, administrative, fiscal, and commercial decentralization are examples of these diversions. According to Rondinelli (1981), administrative decentralization takes four different forms such as deconcentration, delegation, devolution, and deregulation that are discussed below.

❖ De-concentration

De-concentration is most common under the unitary state, which is aimed to disperse decision-making authority, as well as financial and managerial obligations, across the many levels of the central government. It primarily delegated responsibility from central-level authorities to field-level authorities. De-concentration creates a strong field administration that is subject to

the oversight of central government departments. As a result of this provision, the kind of decentralization becomes less effective.

❖ Delegation

Delegation refers to the transfer of responsibility for decision-making and administration of public tasks to semi-autonomous groups, which is a broader type of decentralization. Those semi-autonomous groups would be supervised by the central government but not entirely controlled by it. This type of decentralization gives empowered working units a lot of discretionary decision-making power and funding.

❖ Devolution

Devolution is a type of administrative decentralization that is widely used. When governments devolve activities, they provide quasi-autonomous local government entities with corporate status responsibility for decision-making, funding, and administration. Devolution often shifts service duties to municipalities, who elect their own representatives, raise their own income, and make investment choices independently.

Local governments can use their power and authority to fulfill public responsibilities within visible and legally recognized geographical bounds thanks to devolution. It is the most effective kind of administrative decentralization.

❖ Privatization

Privatization, which refers to the transfer of a business or industry from the public to the private sector, is another kind of decentralization.

The evolution of decentralization in Bangladesh

The governance of the local area is the responsibility of local government. It acts as a representative of the government. Local government in Bangladesh has a long history, with different levels of administration being formed at different times. Ordinances have been passed from time to time to establish local bodies at the village, Thana, District, and Divisional levels. The tasks and responsibilities of local government entities have changed dramatically since their origin in Bangladesh's current local government system dates back to the British colonial period. During the latter half of the nineteenth century, the first effort at building local government institutions was made. From the British colonial period to the present, the

organization, functions, and financial management of local government entities have changed dramatically.

The communities were self-sufficient before colonial authority, according to history. Every hamlet had its own Panchayet or community-based organization. It was made up of all of the village's adult members. For the performance of their customary tasks, Panchayats used to mobilize resources. The Panchayet was founded on popular opinion and grew out of societal necessities. There was no legal foundation for them, and they lacked power.

During the British rule, the Bengal village Chowkidari Act was passed in 1870 with administrative, economic, and political objectives. This paved the way for setting up local government bodies under the law. Under this Act several villages were planned into a Union and Chowkidari Panchayet (Organization) was set up in each Union. Members of the Chowkidari system were treated as government employees rather than villagers' representatives. Panchayats were primarily utilized to aid the state in maintaining law and order as well as tax collection. In terms of development activities, they had no role or purpose. For these reasons, it was considered that the Chowkidari Panchayet needed to be replaced with local government bodies with more authority. The passage of the Bengal Local Self Government Act in 1885 was a crucial step in this direction. Union Committees, Local Government Boards, and District Boards were established as a result of these Acts.

Chowkidari Panchayet and Union Committee were dissolved by the Bengal Village Self-Government Act of 1919, and Union Board and District Board were established in their place. Two-thirds of the Union Board members were elected, while one-third were nominated. In 1946, the nomination system was discontinued. The Union Board's principal responsibilities included maintaining law and order, maintaining roads and bridges, providing health care, charity dispensaries and elementary schools, water supply, and assisting the District Board. Minor criminal offenses may be resolved by the Union Board, which would also have the ability to impose the Union rate.

Local government organizations were established at four tiers during the Pakistan era under the Basic Democracy Order of 1959. Union Council at the Union level, Thana Council at the Thana level, District Council at the District level, and Divisional Council at the Divisional level are the four levels of government. Two-thirds of the members were chosen by the public, while the remaining one-third were appointed by the government. Following the adoption of the constitution, the nomination system was eliminated. Members used to choose a chairman and

a vice-chairman from among themselves. They are also responsible for maintaining the law and order in their region. Agriculture, water supply, education, communications, and social welfare were among the 37 tasks assigned to the Union Council. The Muslim Family and Marriage Ordinance of 1961 also gave the Union Council the ability to establish a conciliation court and gave its members judicial jurisdiction. The Union Council was given the authority to levy taxes on property and other sources in addition to the existing Chowkidari budget by the Basic Democracies Ordinance of 1959 (Siddiqui,2005)

Decentralization efforts in independent Bangladesh

Bangladesh's local government system has undergone several revisions since independence in 1971, under the administrations of various political leaders. The only time the categorization changed was during the peak of municipal government. However, there has been no attempt to transform municipal government into a nonpartisan institution.

During the Sheikh Mujib dictatorship, the Union Council was renamed Union Panchayet, the Thana Council was renamed Thana Development Committee, and the District Council Zila Board was renamed District Council Zila Board. The Union Panchayat was renamed Union Parishad in 1973.

The Local Government Ordinance of 1976, enacted during the Ziaur Rahman era, established a three-tier local government structure. Union Parishad, Thana Parishad, and Zila Parishad were the Union, Thana, and Zila Parishads, respectively. The Union Parishad was given forty responsibilities, including public welfare, law and order, tax collection, and so on. The Thana Parishad lacked revenue-raising authority, and its main source of income was government allowances. As ex-officio chairman of the Parishad, SDO (Sub-Divisional Officer) exercised all executive functions. Swanirvar Gram Sarkar was established in 1980 as a result of a change to the Local Government Ordinance of 1976. It was given the task of increasing food production, eliminating illiteracy, decreasing population increase, and keeping the hamlet in order. However, during the 1982 Martial Law Order, this method was terminated.

During Ershad's reign, Thana became the administrative center, and all development operations were delegated to Thana. Upazila Parishad was given to Thanas. The Upazila Parishad Ordinance was noteworthy in that it aided the government's decentralization efforts. The

chairman held primary power over the Upazila under the Upozila system, and the Upazila Nirbahi Officer (UNO) was his subordinate. As a result, the technique was quite effective.

In 1991, the Bangladesh National Party (BNP) took control when Ershad's government ended, and the Upazila system was abolished. They wanted to exert power at the local level through their elected representatives. In the presence of the Upazila Chairman at the local level, the MPs were unable to consolidate their power. As a result, the system was abolished. However, they were unable to produce a new kind of municipal administration.

Bangladesh's Awami League came to power in 1996. In May 1997, this administration established a local governance panel, which issued a report. Gram(village) Parishad, Union Parishad, Thana/Upazila Parishad, and Zila Parishad are the four levels of local administration suggested by the commission. However, this was not implemented since the BNP administration re-took power and changed the local government structure once more.

When the Caretaker Government took control in 2007, they made it mandatory for the Ups to observe MPs' guidelines. After the Awami League government took office in 2009, the Upazila Parishad Act was established, confirming the central government's sovereignty over the local level through MPs. However, this went against the democratic, decentralized, and good governance principles (Panday, 2011).

Bangladesh's Decentralization Situation

When the central government decentralizes responsibilities, it gives local government bodies control over decision-making, finance, and administration. In Bangladesh, however, it is believed that the central government decentralizes responsibilities to local government organizations by exerting control over them. In reality, Bangladesh's decentralization program is heavily influenced by the ideas of deconcentration and delegation.

The following are the main issues and challenges in the smooth operation of LGIs:

❖ Colonial Maintenance Pattern of Local Government

Bangladesh was a British colony for over 200 years, then it was under Pakistani authority for nearly 30 years. Because it is rooted in a colonial legacy, Bangladesh's local government system is sometimes referred to be colonial. The colonial management style, characterized by elitists and apathetic disposition, is still prevalent today. In Bangladesh, the nomination

arrangement in the local government constitution is the same. Bangladesh's nomination system is devoid of democracy and decentralized local administration.

❖ Political Leadership

Decentralization of local governance is slowed and inactive due to ineffective national political leadership. There exists a solid point of view in favor of an MP's part considering their familiarity with the local condition. Participation of an MP in development activities in LSIs confirms the selection of the important projects to be executed by the local government organizations. They can play a vital role to communicate local needs in parliament. This stabilizes democracy in Bangladesh (Siddiqui, 1994). Conversely, there are opinions that an advisory role of MP's over local government is not favorable to arrange a feasible local government system (Sarker, 2003). Additionally, importantly, their dominance over local development initiatives will provide more opportunities for corruption, politics, and favoritism.

❖ Dependency on Central Government

There is insufficient freedom of the entities at the local level in the matter of spending duties and allocation of resources. Local government entities do not perform a notable role in providing public facilities, such as education and health facilities.

❖ Lack of Power and Authority

The LGIs organizations in Bangladesh have continued to restrict within the authority of particular development tasks from the very beginning. These organizations cannot use power over governing administration (Panday, 2005). Even several central government entities oversee various development activities that are under the LG's scope, such as education, welfare, social welfare, public health, and so on. Even the affiliation agreements between the LG and several central government field level institutions are not adequately explained. In this case, it's safe to presume that the LG has only been given authority to deal with concerns related to development management. In general, the central government's local entity executives are in charge of their activities and responsibilities. As a result, the LG was kept under constant scrutiny by bureaucrats, and power devolution was not used.

❖ Lack of Accountability

Local government organizations have a low level of accountability. Politically elected officials are unable to maintain control over their workforce and hence are unable to provide adequate local services. Inadequate service supply is blamed on both civil service officials and municipal politicians. It lessens their accountability to the people of the area. Furthermore, the local electorate has no idea what resources are available to the local government or how the monies will be used.

❖ Administrative Weakness and Lack of Political Will

The best requirement for policy design and implementation is political will. However, national officials are unwilling to undertake decentralization and local government improvements. The state's political will looks to be so restricted during the decentralization implementation process. Although decentralization is a first political priority, it is clear that the executive branch, parliament, and local level bureaucrats are its primary proponents or opponents. Political leaders and a significant element of the government have not agreed on any of the previous initiatives.

❖ Patron-client Relationship

Patronage is used to support the political framework at the local level. There is always a patron-client connection there. Traditionally, local government support has been regulated by the rural elite. These elites have sympathizers in the countryside. They are, nonetheless, associated with central-level political leaders. These rural-level elites are treated as junior followers by central-level political leaders, who use them for legitimate control, establishing a power base, and gratifying them as vote banks. As a result, these elites have active control over the poor sectors of the population (Sarker, 2006). The transfer of resources from upper levels of government to rural level local government bodies is mostly determined by private or party-political considerations rather than need.

Conclusion

Bangladesh is a centralized country. Since independence, the system of centralized government has been decentralized under different governments. Bangladesh has not yet developed into a fully decentralized country. Because the central government regulates the local government system in different ways. The local government does not have enough power to make decisions. The central-local government relationship continues to remain dominant. Over the last few decades, several substantial changes have been implemented under the banner of "decentralization." As a result, Bangladeshi policy has followed a worldwide trend of promoting decentralization and strengthening local institutions. By moving duties from national and district-level authorities to the lower levels of thana (police post area) and union, these decentralization strategies have aimed to enhance service delivery. Finally, though Bangladesh now lacks true representational decentralization, administrative decentralization does exist.

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